

Reaction of promising rice cultures to leaf scald disease.

Cultivar	Cross	Disease reaction ^a	Cultivar	cross	Disease reaction ^a
		<i>Resistant</i>			
5742	Imp. Sabarmathi/ Sona	3	574 1	Imp. Sabarmathi/ Sona	4
6903	RP5-32/Pankaj	3	6466	Dasal/IR20	4
7150	(PTB10/N136-19) Pankaj	3	7191	RP5-32/Pankaj	5
VL8	–	2	BKB	BKB	4
Rasi	TN1/Co 29	3	KMP106	75-203/IR34	6
Jaya	TN1/T141	2	IR54	–	6
Intan	–	3			<i>Susceptible</i>
KMS5914	Sona/Mahsuri	2	6 254	IR20/IR5-1143	7
		<i>Moderately susceptible</i>	6919	Pankaj/RP270-63-3	8
6056	CR44-35/W12708	5	7296	–	7
			Cauvery	–	8
			Tellahamsa	–	7

^aCD at 5% = 1.89, SEM = 0.94, CV% = 7.23, GM = 18.40. ^a By 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

susceptible checks. Plants were exposed to natural infection and disease incidence was rated using the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. The results are in the table. □

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GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Brown planthopper-resistant japonica varieties developed in Korea

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In Korea, where brown planthopper (BPH) is the most serious rice insect, only hybrid cultivars have been released to farmers as resistant varieties. Among the released cultivars are several japonica varieties, but they are all susceptible to BPH.

Japonica varieties Milyang 64, Milyang 65, and Milyang 66 were developed as new elite lines at Yeongnam Crops Experiment Station in 1981. Milyang 64 was produced from a cross between Milyang 15 and Chok 48-1, and Milyang 65 and 66 were developed from crosses between Milyang 15 and Chok 48-5.

Seedling reactions of rice varieties to BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3 were studied using the seedling bulk test. BPH biotype population increase was tested in a screen-house.

Milyang 64 and 66 were resistant to biotypes 1 and 2 at seedling stage and Milyang 65 was resistant to biotype 1 (Tables 1 and 2). □

Table 1. Reaction of japonica varieties to BPH biotypes 1, 2, and 3.

Variety	Damage rating ^a		
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Milyang 64 (Milyang 15/Chok 48-1)	R	R	S
Milyang 65 (Milyang 15/Chok 48-5)	R	S	S
Milyang 66 (Milyang 15/Chok 48-5)	R	R	S
Milyang 23 (check)	S	S	S
Cheongcheongbyeo (check)	R	S	R
Milyang 63 (check)	R	R	S

^aBased on seedling bulk test. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Table 2. Population buildup of BPH biotypes on rice plants infested at 30 days after transplanting in the nethouse.

Variety	Populations ^a (no.)					
	Biotype 1			Biotype 2		
	45 DT	60 DT	75 DT	45 DT	60 DT	75 DT
Milyang 64	0.2	2.3	2.0	7.3	270.3	–
Milyang 65	3.0	3.8	3.5	55.0	950.0	HB
Milyang 66	1.3	0.6	3.5	1.4	160.0	–
Milyang 23 (check)	46.0	330.0	HB	125.0	HB	HB
Cheongcheongbyeo (check)	0.1	2.0	3.2	25.1	1200.0	HB
Milyang 63 (check)	0.1	1.4	0.2	0.1	110.01	–

^aTotal number of insects per hill. DT = days after transplanting. HB = hopperburned.

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